

EMERGING TRENDS IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: REVIEW ON AI'S ACHIEVEMENTS IN THE WORLD OF SCIENCE

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Abstract. *In this paper, we will explore how artificial intelligence (AI) might evolve in the future and what impact it could have on the development of our civilization. We will also examine the problems that AI integration can help solve in everyday life. Additionally, we will discuss how Moore's Law relates to AI's computational capabilities and how this law could become a limiting factor in performance improvements. The main objective of this study is to demonstrate the significance and value of AI as a transition to the next stage of human development.*

Keywords: CASP - Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction, AlphaFold, Moore's Law.

Introduction

In November 1956, the famous science fiction writer Isaac Asimov published a short story titled "*The Last Question*." In this story, he described a near future in which humanity created a supercomputer with artificial intelligence that was more intelligent than any human. This AI managed to solve numerous problems on a cosmic scale and, at the end of time, restarted the universe itself, thereby preventing the heat death of the universe, also known as maximum entropy.

A 2022 study published by Cambridge University and the University of Oslo discusses the fundamental limitations of AI related to mathematical constraints [7]. These mathematical challenges stem from the inability to find exact algorithms to build the best possible models for specific tasks. This research raises doubts about AI's ability to surpass human intelligence due to both mathematical and computational limits.[1]

In July of the same year, at the CASP (Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction) competition, Google DeepMind's AI, AlphaFold, successfully generated models for 200 million proteins—equivalent to almost all proteins in existence [9]. In comparison, before 2022, humanity had discovered only about 200,000 proteins, significantly changing our perception of AI as a scientific tool.

How Does AI 'Think'?

The term "artificial intelligence" was first introduced by American scientists John McCarthy, Marvin Minsky, Nathaniel Rochester, and Claude Shannon during their summer seminar in 1956.[8]

AI is based on machine learning algorithms that process data to generate the most optimal response. The core of AI is its neural network (ANN), which is a mathematical model simulating the function of a biological neuron.

Each artificial neuron receives input data, multiplies them by weights, and passes them to the next layer of neurons, continuing this process until the data traverse all layers.

Mathematically, this is expressed by the following formula:

$$y = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right)$$

y – output data;

w_i – weights;

x_i – input data;

b – bias;

f(x) – activation function.

After computing the output signal, the network compares it with the correct answer and updates the weights using gradient descent to minimize the error.

AI also utilizes different learning methods, such as supervised and unsupervised learning:

- **Supervised Learning:** Requires large amounts of labeled data. Used in classification, regression, speech, and text recognition tasks.
- **Unsupervised Learning:** Does not require labeled data. Applied in clustering problems.

By using the backpropagation algorithm, the gradient of the error is computed for each weight, allowing the model to adjust and minimize errors.

Why AI is a Step Toward the Next Stage of Development?

According to a study published on July 19, 2016, titled “*The Memory of Science: Inflation, Myopia, and the Knowledge Network*”, the number of scientific publications grows by 4% each year, meaning the number of references doubles every 12 years [5]. This makes research increasingly difficult, forcing scientists to conduct experiments in ever-narrower specializations.

At the same time, German researchers from the Max Planck Institute, Xuemei Gu and Mario Krenn, suggest addressing this issue by using evolving knowledge graphs and machine learning, which allow the prediction of scientific idea trends and their potential impact [3].

Graph

1.

The tendency of growth in data per each year.[2]

Materials and methods:

In this study, we will base our analysis on the research “*AlphaFold2 and its applications in the fields of biology and medicine*” by Zhenyu Yang, Xiaoxi Zeng, Yi Zhao, and Runsheng

Chen, published on March 14, 2023 [9]. We will also consider the deep learning model GNoME, developed by Google’s DeepMind [4]. Our research will aim to calculate how AI affects not only social aspects but also environmental factors by assessing the resource consumption of AI. In addition to these AI models, we will utilize publicly available data on ChatGPT for our calculations.[6]

Over the past century, many biologists have been trying to find an efficient way to determine protein structures. Over five decades, scientists have discovered only about 200,000 different protein structures. Several factors make the task of computing protein structures extremely complex. First, there are a vast number of possible configurations in a protein’s structure—each amino acid in a protein can rotate around its bonds, creating millions of possible forms even for a small protein. This makes traditional computational methods extremely slow. Additionally, amino acid interactions are nonlinear and difficult to predict. The lack of experimental data, due to the high cost and complexity of protein structure analysis methods, further complicates the task.[9]

Since 1961, following Anfinsen’s hypothesis known as “*Anfinsen’s Dogma*”, researchers have been searching for various algorithms to directly compute a three-dimensional (3D) projection of a structure from amino acid sequences. However, Cyrus Levinthal, a biologist from MIT, illustrated how complex and time-consuming such a computation would be. He demonstrated that even a small protein consisting of 35 amino acids could fold in an astronomically large number of ways, taking 200 times the age of the universe to compute.

Despite these challenges, John Moult initiated the CASP (Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction) competition in 1994. The main goal was simple: to develop a computer model that could take an amino acid sequence and determine its structure. A perfect match would receive a score of 100 points, while any result above 90 was considered sufficiently accurate for the structure to be deemed solved. During the first eight CASP competitions, biologists struggled to achieve success, and results remained stagnant. Then, Demis Hassabis, who had recently founded the AI research company DeepMind, introduced AlphaFold.[9]

AlphaFold 1 (AF1) was the first version of the system, based on a standard deep neural network trained on a large dataset of known protein structures. The input data included amino acid sequences and evolutionary alignments, which reflected the mutations preserved across species. This approach helped identify key amino acid pairs essential for protein structure formation.

Instead of directly predicting the 3D shape, AF1 first created a 2D representation showing which amino acids were positioned close to each other. Then, a separate algorithm used this data to fold the protein into its final structure. This approach was the first major breakthrough in AI-based protein structure prediction. Thanks to its methodology, AF1 entered the CASP13 competition and became the most capable model at the time, despite being imperfect, reaching a score of 70. However, DeepMind had yet to surpass the threshold of 90, which led to the development of a much more powerful version—AlphaFold 2 (AF2).

AF2 is the most advanced protein structure prediction model developed by DeepMind. AF2 leverages deep learning neural networks and considers evolutionary conservation of protein structures. Unlike AF1, AF2 processes sequential data using a transformer-based attention mechanism. These transformers allow for the simultaneous analysis of all input data, determining which information is crucial for prediction. AF2 consists of three main modules:

1. **Input Module** – This module analyzes the amino acid sequence, searches for homologs in databases, and performs multiple sequence alignment (MSA) of homologs. AF2

also checks each homolog for existing 3D structures in its database. For homologs, AF2 constructs a matrix of pairwise distances between amino acids. Moreover, although MSA does not explicitly calculate co-evolution, this model extracts and utilizes co-evolutionary information, thanks to a vast number of databases enabling such analysis.

2. **Evoformer Module** – Evoformer processes MSA and pairwise representations, allowing them to exchange information and improve prediction accuracy. This module uses transformers and a specialized attention mechanism to identify key interactions between amino acids.

3. **Structure Module** – The primary function of this module is to transform abstract protein representations into a 3D structure. It takes the single and pairwise representations from the previous modules, as well as the protein backbone consisting of C α , N, and C atoms. A key component is invariant point attention (IPA), which updates the protein representation while ensuring that input transformations produce predictable and consistent output transformations. To enhance its accuracy, AF2 reuses its output data as input at each iteration in a process known as *recycling*.

Through these processes, DeepMind successfully developed a model that outperformed AF1 in every aspect. In CASP14, AF2 ultimately became the competition’s winner, achieving a score of 90 **GDT_TS (Global distance test total score)**. This breakthrough enabled the discovery of nearly all significant protein structures, increasing the number from 150,000 to 200

million in just one year.[9]

Graph 2.

The discovery of all these proteins could enable scientists and medical researchers to develop numerous vaccines for diseases, antidotes for various animal and insect venoms. Previously, humans had to rely on slow, expensive, and low-yield processes. With the availability of these proteins, it will be possible to synthesize these substances efficiently. AF2 is an outstanding example demonstrating how AI can contribute to the advancement of various fields in our time.

Another example of such AI innovation is **GNoME**, also developed by DeepMind. GNoME is a **graph neural network (GNN)** designed to predict the stability of crystalline structures. It was trained using data from the **Materials Project** and was used to generate new candidate crystals.[4]

To verify the accuracy of its predictions, **density functional theory (DFT)** was applied. The use of active learning significantly improved the model's precision, increasing the success rate of predictions from **50% to 80%**, while the search efficiency increased from **less than 10% to over 80%**.

GNoME employs two **pipelines** for discovering stable materials.

- The **structural pipeline** generates candidates based on known crystalline structures.
- The **compositional pipeline** creates new compounds using chemical formulas.

Their stability is then tested using **DFT methods**, and the obtained data are used to enhance the model in subsequent iterations of active learning.

With GNoME, researchers have been able to **discover 2.2 million new crystals**, among which **380,000** are the most stable materials. The discovery of such a large number of crystals is equivalent to **800 years** of accumulated human knowledge, making this AI one of the most valuable tools for humanity.

The most stable materials discovered could serve as promising candidates for experimental synthesis. Among the **GNoME-predicted candidates**, there are materials that may play a key role in the development of cutting-edge technologies, such as:

- **Superconductors** for high-performance computing.
- **Energy-efficient components** for supercomputers.
- **Next-generation batteries**, improving the efficiency of electric vehicles

Graph3.[9]

“About 20,000 of the crystals experimentally identified in the ICSD database are computationally stable. Computational approaches drawing from the Materials Project, Open Quantum Materials Database and WBM database boosted this number to 48,000 stable crystals. GNoME expands the number of stable materials known to humanity to 421,000...”. [4]

Data about the tendency in AI progress over the past 80 years:

Graph 4. (amount of time spent to teach AI)

Graph 5. (amount of milli seconds spent by AI per response)

Problems:

If AI is advancing so rapidly, what challenges might researchers, engineers, and programmers face? In reality, there are many problems, but the most significant ones include:

- **Moore’s Law** – States that every 24 months, the number of transistors on an integrated circuit doubles in quantity.

$$N(y) = N_0 \times 2^{\frac{y}{24}}$$

- N(y) – Number of transistors in year y

- N_0 – Initial number of transistors.

Energy Consumption – More powerful and advanced AI models consume enormous amounts of energy, producing excessive heat.

$$E = P \times t$$

Where:

- E – Energy in joules.
- P – Processor power.
- t – Operating time in seconds.

Regarding Moore's Law, the issue is that it ceased to be valid in 2022, as announced by NVIDIA CEO Jensen Huang. As a result, it is easy to conclude that processor performance will no longer increase as rapidly without a corresponding rise in cost and physical size. This issue directly leads to another problem: increasing energy consumption and subsequent heat dissipation from processors.

Calculations:

We will attempt to calculate the energy consumption and emissions of **GPT-4** and **GPT-3** for comparison.[6]

To begin with, training GPT-3 required a **supercomputer with 285,000 processor cores**, consuming approximately **1,287 megawatt-hours**. The training of **GPT-4**, which is now used in ChatGPT, required around **1,750 megawatt-hours**. Additionally, each AI model consumes energy per query, as shown by the study of **Sakib Siddiki**, which estimates that **GPT-3 consumes 0.0003 kWh per query**, while **GPT-4 consumes 0.0005 kWh per query**.

Convert to Joules (1 MWh = $3.6 * 10^9$ J)

Learning

$$E_{GPT-3} = 1287 * 3.6 * 10^9 = 4.6 * 10^{12} \text{ J}$$

$$E_{GPT-4} = 1750 * 3.6 * 10^9 = 6.3 * 10^{12} \text{ J}$$

Per Query

$$1 \text{ kWh} = 3.6 * 10^6 \text{ J}$$

$$E_{GPT-3(per req)} = 0.0003 * 3.6 * 10^6 = 1080 \text{ J}$$

$$E_{GPT-4(per req)} = 0.0005 * 3.6 * 10^6 = 1800 \text{ J}$$

Assuming GPT-4 processes 10^8 requests per day:

$$E_{GPT-4(day)} = E_{GPT-4(per req)} * 10^8 = 1.8 * 10^{11} \text{ J} = 50 \text{ MWh}$$

$$E_{GPT-4(year)} = 50 * 365 = 18,250 \text{ MWh}$$

If we assume that ChatGPT's data centers are powered by nuclear energy (since there is no confirmed source on OpenAI's energy supply), such as the **South Texas Nuclear Generating Station** or **Comanche Peak Nuclear Power Plant**, then CO₂ emission calculations would be as follows:

0.01 kg of CO₂ per kWh [10]

During learning

$$E_{C_GPT-3} = 1287 * 0.01 * 10^3 = 12870 \text{ kg} = 12.87 \text{ t of CO}_2$$

$$E_{C_GPT-4} = 1750 * 0.01 * 10^3 = 17500 \text{ kg} = 17.5 \text{ t of CO}_2$$

Per Query

$$E_{C_GPT-3(per req)} = 0.01 * 0.0003 = 0.000003 \text{ kg of CO}_2$$

Per day – 300 kg of CO₂

Per year – 109.5 t of CO₂

$$E_{C_GPT-4(per\ req)} = 0.01 * 0.0005 = 0.000005 \text{ kg of CO}_2$$

Per day – 500 kg of CO₂

Per year – 182.5 t of CO₂

- Training GPT-4 required **6.3 terajoules** of energy and produced **17.5 tons of CO₂** (**4.6 terajoules and 12.87 tons for GPT-3**).

- Maintaining GPT-4 for **one year** consumes approximately **18,250 MWh** of energy and produces **182.5 tons of CO₂** (**109.5 tons for GPT-3**).

- A **single GPT-4 query** consumes **1,800 J** (**1,080 J for GPT-3**).

Discussion:

The obtained data highlight the importance of **energy consumption in AI** and how significantly it impacts the environment. If similar training data were available for **AlphaFold** or **GNoME**, similar calculations could be made for them.

However, the main issue is that if **new energy extraction methods** or **optimization techniques for AI training** are not considered, we risk drastically increasing global pollution and heating the planet within a short period.

Given the growing **public interest** in AI technologies, the problem of energy consumption is **not only likely to persist** but also **intensify over time**. Therefore, it is critical to **start addressing energy consumption and emissions now**.

Conclusion:

Ultimately, we can conclude that **AI technologies are evolving at an unprecedented pace**. However, if no **new breakthroughs** occur in the **energy sector** or **quantum computing**, the potential for AI to **drive scientific breakthroughs** could become **not only difficult to achieve but also environmentally unsustainable**.

Fortunately, companies such as **IBM, Google, and Intel** are already developing **supercomputers with quantum computing capabilities** using **qubits**, offering hope for a more energy-efficient and sustainable future.

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